

Tellurium Alkoxides

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Tellurium isopropoxide has been synthesised by the sodium alkoxide method. The tellurium alkoxide, thus prepared, has been used as a starting material for the synthesis of a large number of alkoxides (methoxide, ethoxide, *n*-butoxide, isobutoxide, *sec.*-butoxide, *t*-butoxide, isoamyl oxide and *t*-amyl oxide) by alcohol-interchange technique. All the alkoxides with the only exception of tellurium *t*-butoxide, which is a white crystalline solid, are liquids which could be distilled under reduced pressure.

Two tellurium alkoxides (methoxide and ethoxide) were synthesised for the first time by Meerwein and Bersin¹ by the interaction of tellurium tetrachloride and the corresponding sodium alkoxide.

Dupuy² obtained tellurium methoxide, ethoxide, *n*-butoxide, and *n*-amyl oxide by suspending $\text{TeCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ in the corresponding alcohol, followed by the addition of the corresponding solution of sodium alkoxide in cold. The reaction mixture was refluxed till the evolution of ammonia had ceased, thereby indicating completion of the reaction:

(where R is Me, Et, *n*-Bu, and *n*-amyl group).

The preparation and properties of alkoxides and allied compounds of several elements³⁻¹⁷ have been the subject of detailed study in our laboratories and a considerable amount of

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work has been published in the last few years. In view of the above scanty and scattered literature available on the chemistry of tellurium alkoxides, it was considered worthwhile to make a systematic and detailed study of tellurium alkoxides by similar techniques.

Tellurium isopropoxide has been prepared by treating tellurium tetrachloride and sodium isopropoxide in a mixture of isopropanol and benzene.

The presence of benzene in the reaction mixture makes the separation of sodium chloride easier by reducing its solubility in alcohol.

The tellurium isopropoxide, thus prepared, could be distilled under reduced pressure and was further used for the preparation of various alkoxides, employing the alcohol-interchange technique.

(where R is Me, Et, Buⁿ, Bu^{sec}, Bu^t, isoamyl, and *t*-amyl group).

These alkoxides could be distilled under reduced pressure, except the *t*-butoxide which is a white crystalline solid and could be sublimed.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the reagents were dried by the methods reported earlier¹⁰. Tellurium tetrachloride used was a B. D. H. product, which was analysed before use.

Tellurium was estimated in the elementary form, using aqueous solutions of sulphur dioxide and hydrazine hydrochloride as precipitating agents. The alkoxy content was estimated in ethoxy and isopropoxy derivatives by hydrolysing the compounds with alkali in presence of benzene. The ethanol and isopropanol liberated were fractionated azeotropically and estimated by the oxidimetric method¹⁶.

Tellurium Isopropoxide.—To tellurium tetrachloride (10 g.), dissolved in isopropanol (20 ml) and cooled by ice, were added 4 moles of sodium isopropoxide (3.412 g. of sodium dissolved in 50 ml of isopropanol) with constant shaking. The reaction was exothermic. Benzene was added and the contents were refluxed for an hour. The excess of the solvent was distilled. On drying the contents under reduced pressure at the room temperature, a colorless liquid was obtained which distilled at 76°/0.5mm (50%, 6.5 g.). [Found: Te, 34.98; OPrⁱ, 65.14. Calc. for Te(OPrⁱ)₄: Te, 35.06; OPrⁱ, 64.94%].

It fumes in air, spontaneously hydrolyses, and decomposes even at the room temperature. On keeping in a cool place, the decomposition could be totally checked.

Higher Alkoxides of Tellurium by Alcohol-interchange Technique

Synthesis of Tellurium n-Butoxide.—*n*-Butanol (10 g.) was added to tellurium isopropoxide (2.71 g.), followed by addition of benzene. The reaction was exothermic. The contents were refluxed under the column for 2 hr. and the isopropanol was slowly removed azeotropically with benzene at 72°. Excess of alcohol and benzene were distilled and the contents after being dried under reduced pressure at the room temperature provided a colorless liquid, distilling at 150°/0.8 mm (84.86%, 2.87g.). [Found: Te, 30.47. Te(OBu)₄ requires Te, 30.37%].

For brevity, the results of synthesis of higher alkoxides have been summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Reactions of tellurium isopropoxide with higher alcohols.

S.No.	Reactants.	Product.	Yield.	%Tellurium.		Alcohol in azeotrope.		Reflux period.
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	
Tellurium isobutoxide.								
1.	Tellurium isopropoxide (3.38 g.) + isobutanol (15.05 g.)	Colorless liquid distilling at 127°/1.5 mm	3.75 g. (96.14%)	30.12	30.37	..	..	2 hr.
Tellurium sec.-butoxide.								
2.	Tellurium isopropoxide (2.56 g.) + sec.-butanol (12.6g.)	Colorless liquid, distilling at 122°/2.5 mm	2.95 g. (100%)	30.25	30.37	30.25	..	..
Tellurium t-butoxide.								
3.	Tellurium isopropoxide (2.4 g.) + t-butanol (10.g.)	White crystalline solid, subliming at 150°/2.5 mm	2.67 g. (96.18%)	29.78	30.37	1.623	1.584	..
Tellurium isoamyl oxide.								
4.	Tellurium isopropoxide (2.9g.) + isoamyl alcohol (15.29 g.)	Light orange liquid, distilling at 162°/0.7 mm	3.72 g. (99.63%)	26.56	26.60	..	..	..
Tellurium t-amyl oxide.								
5.	Tellurium isopropoxide (2.7g.) t-amyl alcohol (12.24 g.)	Colorless liquid, distilling at 108°/0.4 mm	3.35 g. (99.82%)	26.73	26.80	1.855	1.785	..

Tellurium Ethoxide.—Ethanol (10 g.) was added to tellurium isopropoxide (2.28 g.), thereby causing an exothermic reaction. On drying the contents at the room temperature under reduced pressure, a colorless liquid, distilling at 107-107.5°/5 mm, was obtained. It decomposes even at the room temperature on keeping; yield. 1.82 g. (94.39%). [Found: Te, 40.69; OEt, 57.79. Te(OEt)₄ requires Te, 41.43; OEt, 58.57%].

Tellurium Methoxide.—To tellurium isopropoxide (1.18 g.) was added methanol (10 g.). The reaction was exothermic. The contents were dried at the pump at the room tempera-

ture and thus a white crystalline solid was obtained. It distilled at $115^{\circ}/9$ mm, yield 97.36%, 0.725g. [Found: Te, 51.07. $\text{Te}(\text{OMe})_4$ requires Te, 50.68%].

It is very susceptible to moisture and fumes spontaneously on exposure to atmosphere.

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